

Linkage of students' Learning styles to their achievement in mathematics at Grade X in Punjab

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Abstract

This study was taken in two districts of province Punjab. The districts were Sahiwal from central Punjab and Mian Wali from the upper Punjab. The purpose of this study was to explore relationship between learning styles and achievement in mathematics of the students at secondary level in Punjab, Pakistan. This research was descriptive. Total six hundred forty participated from both localities. Two types of tools were administered for quantitative data collection one was achievement test and second was learning style inventory. Researcher himself visited the sample schools and after seeking permission of the relevant school heads conducted the tests form male and female schools. Before test administration both tools were translated to urdu and both tools were administered in English with urdu translation for the convenience of the local students. After test administration the results were compiled by using SPSS Software using statistics of frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviations and tabulated accordingly. For further detailed analysis, Analysis of variance, t-test, correlations and regression analysis was also applied. Other than these tests comparison of male / female, rural/ urban, public/ private was also done. One the basis of the findings it was concluded that achievement score was highest for the students who learned with visual and auditory learning styles. It is recommended to arrange multimedia projectors, utilization of mathematics softwares, and auditory aids for better learning of the students in mathematics class rooms and online centralized discussion boards, were students may submit their queries from the subject experts.

Keywords: Mathematics learning styles, sensory learning styles, Achievement test, Mathematics class rooms

Introduction

There are four levels of education in Pakistan up to intermediate. PECTA authority deals with primary and middle level and Board of Intermediate and Secondary Education BISE serves for matric and intermediate (Ciss, 2019). Every field of daily life has some application of mathematics in one way or other (Hodanova, 2016). Mathematics have gained reputation as a basic subject for learning science and technology (Gimba, Hassan, Yaki, & Chado, 2018). Every person is part of global work force with out difference of colour and creed (Shrestha & Heisler, 2011). Mathematics is playing pivotal role (Hamidah, 2022). Skilled labour can be produced by Quality education in mathematics (Hodanova, 2016). Every person has specific capacity for mathematics education (Virgana, 2019). For proper learning of mathematics its terms, symbols, formulae and theorems need special understanding (Parker Waller, 2016). Mathematics learning styles can affect the achievement of the students (Bramlett & Herron, 2009). **Rationale for the Study**

Knowledge of modern technology base upon pre-knowledge of mathematics (Bosman, 2018). Mathematics produce work force to serve the society (Cemen, 1987). Suitable learning process and environment is necessary for mathematics learning (Bursal, 2006). Knowledge of students' learning style can ease the delivery of the mentor, instructor and teacher (Hirsh, 2020). Learning difficulty needs to be addressed in all branches of mathematics in Pakistan (Naveed, 2016). Through proper administrative efforts achievement of students can be enhanced in mathematics (Naveed, 2016). Learning style is important for class room instruction which plays central role for academic achievement of students (Anyamene, 2022). Learning style means; preference on how they "receive and process information" (Felder & Silverman, 1988, p. 674). Visual and verbal learning styles can affect academic achievement of the students (Cornelius, 2019). Verbal mathematical intelligence has leading influence on achievement but it is not a strong predictor of student's achievement (Xhomara, 2022). There was no significant difference in the mathematics achievement goals based on learning style (Ignacio, 2017). Information gathering regarding sensory style improves learning environment (Thammanna, 2017).

1.1 Objectives of the Study

In present study researcher intended his focus on;

1. To Investigate sensory learning styles of the students for mathematics learning and compare by gender, area and sector of institution.
2. To suggest the most preferred style for learning mathematics.

1.3 Research Questions

The researcher tried to find answer of the questions;

1. Do the learners use sensory styles for learning mathematics?
2. Can learning style affect achievement of the students?

1.4 Statement of the Study

Mathematics learners generate economic growth (Anyamene, 2022). Learning and teaching of mathematics need to be revised according to modern needs (Ali, 2010). We all need to be very vocal

for mathematics talks (Sheerazi, 2000). Mathematics learning style can change one's way of thinking (Ali, 2010). Due to overcrowded class rooms and lack of resources the learnings ways of students are given very rare considerations (Naveed, 2016). Limited use of sensory techniques drops achievement of students during assessment (Margoum, 2022).

1.2 Review of Related Literature

Student-centered teaching practices had a positive and significant effect on the student's mathematics achievement (Emanet, 2021). Rote memory reduces active participation of the students in mathematics class rooms and using refrain students from building new concepts (Emanet, 2021). Addition of daily life problems in mathematics curriculum reduce cramming support critical thinking among the student's (Reys, Lindquist, Lambdin & Smith, 2007). Trained teacher produced good achievement score or students (Vania & Xin, 2014). Educationists have recommended to make education, need based for society (Margoum, 2022). Learning style means; preference on how they "receive and process information" (Felder & Silverman, 1988, p. 674). Students who prefer visual learning, tend to learn by images, diagrams and concrete objects (Ahmad, 2014). Their achievement is remarkable if test contains visual figures, sketches and diagrams (Fadiana, 2015). Look, observe and imagine are words to seek their attention (Adeniji, 2015). Auditory learners rely on recorded lessons and are good in group discussions (Balhan & Eisa, 2007). Auditory learners feel hard to observe and read, they mostly rely on their listening power and comfortable with oral assessment (Fadiana, 2015). Auditory students can do factorization orally, State, solve substitute are words to make them attentive (Hardy, 2010). The kinesthetic learning prefer hands on activity (Dunn, 1995). They use trial-and-error method of learning (Tahir, 2021). Such learners gain through multiple tracks of tasks (Morgan, 2019). Kinesthetic learners are good athletes, counsellors, choreographers and enterprisers (Rameli, et al., 2014). They are good in projects (La Ode Ahmad Jazuli, 2019)

Methodology

Present study deals with quantitative data as it is obtained when the variable being studied is measured along a scale that indicate the degree of involvement of a variable (Jack R. Fraenkel, 2008). Survey method is quantitative and belongs to positivistic paradigm. (Sinaga, 2022). For this study survey method was employed to collect the required data.

Research design

Research design for the present study was quantitative. Two tools were developed for the current research study. After literature review tool regarding learning styles inventory LSI was adopted (Babich, 2003). Achievement test was developed by researcher under the supervision of mathematics experts. These tools were got validated by the relevant experts and then administered after removing language barrier and pilot study by the researcher himself in both districts of Punjab province.

Research instruments

Research had two tools i.e achievement test and learning style inventory. Researcher travelled to the districts for administering tests and data collection from 10th grade male and

female students. After pilot study and knowing difficulty index of items some items were replaced.

Tool -01 Learning styles inventory for students

Learning style inventory was adapted from VARK model (Mills, 1992) . Another tool was CITE learning style inventory (Babich, 1996). This tool consisted of fifty items under four sensory domains. These four sensory domains were Visual, auditory, kinesthetic and read/write learning styles.

Sr. Type of sensory learning style

- 1 : Visual learning style
- 2 : Auditory learning style
- 3 : Kinesthetic learning style
- 4 : Read/Write learning style

(Babich, 2003).

Tool -02 Achievement Test for Students

This tool comprised of seven domains on the different branches of mathematics. Each domain contained seven items for assessment. To avoid the subjectivity and ensure objectivity all the items were objective type. These items were got validated from relevant experts and made ready for test administration after pilot study

Chapter wise distribution of items

Unit	Description	Number of Items	Percentage
1 st	Quadratic Equations	Seven	Fourteen %
2 nd	Concept of Quadratic Equations	//	//
3 rd	Variation	//	//
4 th	Partial Fraction	//	//
5 th	Sets and Functions	//	//
6 th	Basic Statistics	//	//
7 th	Introduction to Trigonometry	Eight	Sixteen %
Total		Fifty	

Population

Grade X students belonging to all genders, localities and sectors of Punjab were taken as population.

Target Population

Target population was confined to only two districts for study, these 10th class male / female students belonging to public/ private schools with residence of urban/ rural areas of Punjab were taken as target population.

BISE	Student strength	Total
1. All Boards total students		11,06,478

Ciss data of Boards

(Iqbal, 2019)

Sample

A sample of six hundred forty students made the sample of the present study belonging to the relevant districts of grade X.

Sampling

Form the target population sample was taken through multistage sampling technique. Whole Punjab region was divided into two major regions namely Upper Punjab, and Central Punjab. Sahiwal district was taken from central Punjab and Mian Wali was taken from Upper Punjab.

Data collection

There were thirty-six districts of Punjab province. Only two districts are taken from each region through convenient sampling. Then from each district only sixteen schools, eight from urban area and eight from rural area, out of these schools four were boys' schools and rest of four were girls' schools.

Data collection scheme (From one District)

Urban School students				Rural Schools students				Total Schools in one District
Public		Private		Public		Private		
Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	
02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	16

Gender wise scheme of data collection

Total schools in two districts = 32

No. of students from each school = 20

No. of students one district = $16 \times 20 = 320$

No. of students in two districts = $320 \times 2 = 640$

Data collection scheme (From Two Districts)

Urban				Rural				Total Schools in two Districts
Public		Private		Public		Private		
Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	
80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	640

The district's schools were drawn on convenient basis; however, the selection of the students was made based on simple random sampling.

Results and discussion

Present study was conducted in two renowned and populous districts of Punjab province. Total six hundred forty participated from both localities. Two types of tools were administered for quantitative data collection one was achievement test and second was learning style inventory. Researcher himself visited the sample schools and after seeking permission of the relevant school principals, head masters and subject experts who facilitated in conduction the tests form male and female schools. Before test administration both tools were translated to urdu and both tools were administered in English with urdu translation for the convenience of the local students. After test administration the data analysis was made by using SPSS Software using statistics of frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviations and tabulated accordingly, finally results were compiled. For further detailed analysis, Analysis of variance, t-test, correlations and regression analysis was also applied. Other than these tests comparison of male / female, rural/ urban, public/ private was also done.

Five-point Likert scale criteria for decision making

Score/ Decision value	Description
3.0	Neutral
4.0-5.0	Highly positive
3.0-4.0	Positive
2.0-3.0	Negative
1.0-2.0	Highly negative

Comparisons of means and standard deviations of student's responses regarding various learning styles

N= 640

VU= Visual Numeric, AN= Auditory Numeric, K=Kinesthetic and

R / W= Read / Write LS= Learning style.

LS	M	SD
VN	3.77	0.64
AN	3.70	0.62
K	3.55	0.61
R / W	3.69	0.67
Overall	3.68	0.63

Table shows as a whole comparison of students' responses about using learning styles for learning mathematics on five-point Likert scale. Total participants students were 640 from both districts the Punjab from the sample districts.

According to decision criteria, neutral or decision value of the mean was 3.0. Comparison table indicated that overall mean score was (M = 3.68) of the learning styles, which revealed that mean value was greater decision mean score (M=3.0). It was very strong indication which clarified that students have used and practiced sensory learning styles for mathematics learning. It is pertinent to describe the students showed most favorable responses for Visual Numeric Learning Style Mean is (M=3.77) and standard deviation (SD=0.64), as decision level or neutral level was 3.0 Opinion was above 3, hence respondents have reacted positively and above the decision mean (3.0) or neutral mean. This indicated that the students were inclined to use visual style. On the other hand, least responses of the students were observed for subscale kinesthetic learning style mean (M= 3.55) standard deviation 0.61. The mean value for Kinesthetic learning style (M = 3.55) was also greater than neutral mean value (M=3.0). This result indicated that kinesthetic learning style was also practiced by the students. As kinesthetic style is based upon activity based and need active participation of the learner, There are chances that teacher' style of teaching may have affected the learning style of the student. One more worth noticing aspect was; mean was again above the decision mean value. The respondents have recorded their opinion positively.

From above descriptive statistics it is worth mentioning that mean score for all learning styles was positive and above neutral mean value. For the sake of better understanding mean scores of learning styles can be presented in following descending order.

3.7735 > 3.7014 > 3.6875 > 3.5528 or in descriptive manner it can be

Written as,

Mean of Learning styles practiced for mathematics learning;

Visual Numeric > Auditory Numeric > Read / Write > Kinesthetic

Points of discussion.

Mean values were found to be positive and varied from M=3.55 to M= 3.77. Overall mean score M=3.68 indicated that mean value was great than decision mean which was 3.0 confirmed that students used all the four learning styles. Results indicated that all learning styles were used by the students for learning. One more result was major learning style of the students was visual learning style whereas kinesthetic learning students have got least importance. This study results satisfied first objective of learning style inventory and research study. Research results matched and were aligned with research findings of many research studies (Adeniji, 2015;Adnan, 2013;Ahmad, 2014;Aljaberi, 2015;Anggoro, 2019;Anyamene, 2022;Awang, 2017;Emanet, 2021;Aydn, 2015;Babich, 2003;Babich, 1996;Cardino, 2020).

Gender wise analysis of variance for students' responses about learning styles

N=640, N= 320 (Male), N = 320 (Female)

Sr.	Learning style	Gender	M	SD.	F- Value	P-Value/ Sig.
01	V N.	Male	3.77	0.63	0.03	0.86
		Female	3.77	0.65		

02	A N.	Male	3.67	0.63	2.64	0.11
		Female	3.72	0.61		
03	KS	Male	3.59	0.62	3.23	0.07
		Female	3.54	0.61		
04	R / W	Male	3.67	0.71	0.40	0.53
		Female	3.69	0.61		

Table revealed the gender wise comparison of learning styles. Results of ANOVA at level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ revealed that P- values were not significant for all four scales. Results based on students' responses indicated that gender had no significant effect on learning styles adopted by the students.

Analysis of Variance results for Public and private student's responses for mathematics learning styles

N=640 , N(Public)= 320, N (Private) =320

Learning styles	Sector	F	t- value	M	SD	Sig.
VN	Public	.294	.039	3.77	0.64	.588
	Private			3.77	0.63	
AN	Public	3.123	-3.356	3.65	0.63	.077
	Private		-3.356	3.74	0.60	
KS	Public	2.712	-1.422	3.55	0.61	.100
	Private		-1.422	3.58	0.62	
R /	Public	.969	-.203	3.68	0.69	.325
	Private		-.203	3.68	0.63	

Table depicted the responses of the public and private students about practice of the learning styles. Table revealed that there is no significant difference between the opinion of the public and private students about the use of mathematics learning styles as p-value of each learning style was greater than 0.05.

Analysis of variance for urban and rural student's responses for mathematics learning styles

N=640, N(Urban)= 320, N (Rural) =320

Learning styles	Locality	F	t- value	M	SD	Sig.
VN	Urban	.303	-1.036	3.75	0.65	.582
	Rural		-1.036	3.78	0.63	
AN	Urban	9.763	1.026	3.71	0.66	.002
	Rural		1.026	3.68	0.58	

KS	Urban	44.357	-.292	3.56	0.68	.000
	Rural		-.292	3.57	0.54	
R /	Urban	16.817	3.377	3.73	0.72	.000
	Rural		3.377	3.63	0.59	

Table depict the responses of the urban and rural students about practice of the learning styles. Table revealed that there was significant difference between the opinion of the urban and rural students about the use of “auditory numeric learning” ,“kinesthetic style” and “read /write” style as p-value of learning styles was less than 0.05. Table also revealed that there is no significant difference between the opinion of the urban and rural students about the use of visual numeric learning style as p-value of learning style was greater than 0.05. For “Auditory Numeric” difference was significant which indicated that there is difference of opinion between rural and urban students. Moreover, the mean of urban students (3.71) was higher than the mean of the rural students (3.68). Similarly significant difference was also found in the opinion of rural and urban students for “Read /Write” style Their mean score of urban students (3.73) was also larger as compared to mean of rural students (3.63). while in case of “Visual Numeric” and “kinesthetic” style users’ opinion of the rural students got more weightage and rural students shown positive tendency towards these styles.

Analysis of variance for visual numeric learning styles of the students

Sr. No.	Dependent Variable	(1) District	(2) District	Mean Difference	SD	F-Value	P-Value/ Sig.
01	Visual Numeric	Sahiwal	Mian Wali	0.25*	2.12	39.6	.000

Table revealed the comparison of learning styles between both districts. P-Value indicated that there was significant difference among the districts regarding visual numeric learning styles. Sahiwal district students showed positive opinion regarding visual learning style as compared to Mian Wali Results are significant if the level of significance has value 0.05 or below this value (Eisenhauer, 2008). Area wise results of ANOVA showed comparison of learning styles of the students. Results fulfill the requirement of the research objective learning style inventory. Research indicated that the area wise visual learning styles were found to be significant for both districts that showed the students used visual learning style.

Analysis of variance results for students’ responses for auditory numeric learning styles

Sr. No.	Dependent Variable	(1) District	(2) District	Mean Difference	SD	F-Value	P-Value/ Sig.
01	Auditory	Sahiwal	Mian	0.19*	2.13	19.79	.001

Numeric	Wali
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Table revealed the comparison of auditory numeric learning styles among two districts. Results indicated in table revealed that difference was significant for auditory numeric learning style as its value is 0.001 which is less than 0.005. Sahiwal district students showed positive opinion regarding auditory learning style as compared to Mian Wali. Results are considered significant if the level of significance with value 0.05 or below this value (Eisenhauer, 2008). Area wise results of ANOVA showed comparison of learning styles of the students. Results fulfill the requirement of the research objective of learning style inventory. Research indicated that the area wise auditory learning styles was found to be significant for both districts that showed the students used auditory learning style.

Co-relation analysis between learning styles and achievement by using Pearson correlation formula.

N = 640

VU= Visual Numeric, AN= Auditory Numeric, K=Kinesthetic and

R / W= Read / Write LS= Learning style.

LS	M (Achievement)	M (LS)	SD	r	Sig.
VN	35.53	3.77	.64	0.30**	.000
AN		3.70	.68	0.34**	.000
K		3.57	.61	0.14	.000
R / W		3.68	.66	0.23	.000

Table reflected relationship of learning styles with achievement test score of the respondents. Value of Pearson r was significant for all styles, moreover results were more positive for visual and auditory styles. Though the correlation remained moderate positive for visual numeric and auditory numeric style and achievement score of the students. Table reflected that the significant relationship in case of read/ write style and achievement score of the students. It was evident from table that there was a positive co relation between the achievement score of Read/ Write style and over all achievement score of the student. However, relationship between Read/ Write Style and achievement score of the students was low moderate. Row 03 of table exhibited that the relationship is significant and there was a positive co relation between the achievement score for kinesthetic style and over all achievement score of the student, but it was positive.

However, there was weak positive relationship found between kinesthetic style and achievement score of the students. Moreover, strongest correlation was found with auditory numeric style and least value was found for kinesthetic style.

Statistically it can be concluded that correlation between mathematics achievement and all sensory learning styles was significant and positive. There was weak positive relationship found between kinesthetic style and achievement score of the students. These study results are aligned to previous study, which related the auditory numeric style of students as effective source to produce mathematics fluency among students (Nayazik, 2022)

Regression analysis for visual numeric learning styles and achievement score the students.

N= 640

LS Practices	Beta	t-value	Sig.	R ²
	B			
VN Subscale-01	.11	3.63	.000	.128

Table represented regression analysis between visual learning style for learning mathematics and achievement score of the respondents. Table gave approximately thirteen percent of the variance as explained by the regression model. results revealed that the visual learning style affected students' achievement score in mathematics significantly and visual learning style contributed towards achievement of the students. Large and positive t -values 3.63, indicated that learning style subscales were different from each other and has direct effect on achievement (i.e achievement on this scale was above the mean score), Whereas negative values would have indicated reversal effect i.e achievement on this scale was below the mean.

Regression analysis is done when prediction was required between two parameters (Gupta, 2017). In this research linear regression is used as there is linear relation between the given parameters it was aligned to results of Tyagi (Tyagi, 2022). Regression analysis showed that visual learning style affected students' achievement score in mathematics significantly. Large and positive t -values 3.63, indicated that learning style subscales were different from each other as described by Devore (Devore, 2003). Personal learning style of student has direct effect on achievement, (Ozerem, 2015).

Conclusion

One the basis of the findings it was concluded that achievement score was highest for the students who learned with auditory and visual learning styles. It is further clear from the tables that students were more inclined towards the auditory learning style. There was found no significant difference between the visual numeric learning styles of rural and urban students but significant for rest of the styles. For public and private students there was no difference found. In case of gender wise comparison, the results were significant for auditory numeric style only.

Recommendations

1. It is recommended to arrange multimedia projectors for mathematics learning. For utilization of mathematics softwares, and auditory aids for better learning of the students in mathematics class rooms.
2. Arrange a centralized discussion board for students and teachers where students may get answers for their queries.

Delimitation of the Study

Having limited time and resources, the study was delimited to,

1. Comparison of only two districts of the province, Punjab, Pakistan.
2. Students belonging to grade X only, who have completed their eighty percent syllabus in the terminal class.
3. The learners who preferred to choose science group with elective mathematics of grade X.
4. Only Twenty students were examined from each school, Whichever the strength school had, but only said participants were allowed for assessment.

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